

Tapewrapped Phenolic Composites Reinforced with Advanced Carbon Fabrics

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ABSTRACT

Carbon textiles are widely used in ablative and thermal insulating applications because of their low density, low conductivity, dimensional stability, strength at high temperatures, flexibility, low cost and nonmelting characteristics. For over two decades, these carbonaceous materials have been manufactured primarily by controlled pyrolysis of continuous filament rayon. Recent attention has focused on other organic precursor fibers like polyacrylonitrile (PAN) and pitch. Commercially available carbon fabrics were found to exhibit high strengths and uniformity, but they were deficient in insulative characteristics and chemical purity. To alleviate these limitations, a variety of developmental carbon fabrics were manufactured at non-standard processing temperatures and conditions. These specialty fabrics were prepregged with phenolic resin and then fabricated into tapewrapped cylinders. Engineering properties were measured and correlated with the fabric characteristics. Composites containing the developmental carbon fabrics exhibited a good balance of insulative, ablative and mechanical properties.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon textiles are widely used in thermal protection composites because of their low thermal conductivity, dimensional stability at high temperatures, low density, nonflammability, low cost and availability in a variety of physical forms. These fabrics are typically combined with a char-forming resin (like phenolic) to yield thermally insulative composites (1-3).

Carbon textiles are manufactured by controlled pyrolysis of woven cloth or by weaving carbon yarns (tows) into a desired fabric construction. Typical properties of commercially available carbon fabrics are shown in Table 1. The rayon-based carbon fabrics were the lightest weight and thinnest, because they were woven from low density, single ply, 720 filament yarn. The rayon-based carbon fabrics were also the lowest in tensile breaking strength, ie, about 30 to 43 lbf/in. (3.9 to 4.9 N/m). Developmental pitch-based carbon fabrics were slightly higher in strength, but the commercially available materials were about three times stronger. The highest strength fabrics were composed of PAN-based carbon yarns. Breaking strengths up to 390 lbf/in. (44.1 N/m) were recorded.

The objectives of this program were to (a) determine the suitability of available carbon fabrics for thermal protection composites and (b) develop new carbon fabrics with an improved balance of insulative, ablative and mechanical properties.

CARBON FIBERS

Carbon fibers are typically obtained at maximum process temperatures of about 1,475° to 2,900°F (802° to 1,593°C), while graphite fibers are produced at higher heat treatment temperatures of 4,000°F (2,204°C) or higher. Fibers having a carbon content up to 92 weight % have been designated carbon fibers, whereas higher carbon contents have resulted in a graphite classification. Neither of these classifications have been satisfactory because rayon and acrylic fibers are non-graphitizable materials. They are incapable of being substantially converted by heat treatment to large crystallites having a three-dimensional structure characteristic of polycrystalline graphite.

Carbon fibers are characterized by lower density, higher surface area, higher electrical resistivity, lower thermal conductivity, and lower carbon contents as compared to graphite fibers. The carbon fibers have a greater tendency to pick up moisture and are easily wet with resin.

A review of the thermal and electrical properties of carbon and graphite fibers suggested that low thermal conductance fibers could be obtained by a disordered carbon microstructure and lower-than-standard thermal processing temperatures (4-6). High purity, 3,000 filament PAN yarn was obtained from a Japanese source and carbonized at maximum temperatures of 1,652°F (900°C) to 2,462°F (1,350°C). The decrease in axial fiber thermal conductivity as a function of lower process temperature is illustrated in Figure 1. Measurements performed on pitch-based carbon fibers revealed similar trends, although their higher degree of crystalline orientation resulted in slightly higher thermal conductance values.

Developmental Carbon Fabrics

A variety of experimental carbon fabrics were manufactured from special processed PAN-based and pitch-based yarns and tows. In the first method, PAN oxidized yarns or tows were woven into the desired fabric construction and then pyrolyzed into the attendant carbon form. This manufacturing method produced low quality fabric. The strength was also low because of the difficulty in restraining the fill yarns during processing various constructions. The preferred method was to manufacture the carbon yarn or tow at nonstandard (lower) processing temperatures and then weave it into fabric. For pitch-based materials, however, a suitable low cost fabric was obtained by weaving oxidized yarn into fabric and then pyrolyzing at the desired temperature. Yarn restraint during pyrolysis was not required because of the fixed precursor fiber molecular structure.

Phenolic Prepregs

Phenolic prepreg material was developed to obtain fabric reinforced composites. Both commercially available and developmental fabrics were impregnated with phenolic or carbon powder filled phenolic resins. Compared to available rayon-based carbon fabrics, the developmental fabric prepreg had a lower resin content and reduced resin wettability. Increased fiber microporosity, altered surface chemistry and high moisture content were believed to be the causative factors. Nevertheless, suitable prepregs were obtained with resin contents on the order of 32 to 36 weight %, five to seven % volatiles and four to six % flow.

Cylindrical Composites

Thermal protection composites are usually composed of phenolic resins with a carbon fabric at a predetermined angle to the surface. This type of composite offers the best balance of insulation, mechanical properties and fabricability.

Hollow cylinders were prepared by the tapewrapping fabrication method to gain experience with the developmental prepregs, obtain baseline composite properties, and to identify candidate materials for follow-on evaluation efforts. The developmental, non-surface treated carbon fabrics were prepregged with an unfilled phenolic resin, cut into tapes at 45° to the warp direction, sewn together into continuous strips, and slit into the desired tape width. The bias tape was hand fed onto a cylindrical rotating metal mandrel, as shown in Figure 2. The wrapped composite was debulked in an autoclave to reduce its porosity. The cylinders were then machined to a predetermined outside diameter that was adequate to fit into the female cure fixture. After machining, the cylinders were removed from the mandrel and loaded into the cure fixture together with a bleeder cloth and a rubber bag. Vacuum was applied and the assembly placed into a hydroclave. The part was then incrementally pressurized to 1,000 psi (6.89 MPa) and cured. The cylindrical specimens obtained were nine in. in length, nine in. in outside dimension and one-half in. in thickness. The fabric angle was 20° to the axial direction.

Engineering Properties

Ablative, thermophysical, chemical and mechanical properties of the 20° tapewrapped carbon fabric/phenolic composites were measured at room and high temperatures. These engineering properties were compared to values obtained for baseline rayon-based carbon fabric/phenolic composites to permit the identification of attributes, limitations and improvement needs.

Ablation. Ground-based test facilities have been extensively used to determine the ablative characteristics of carbon fabric reinforced phenolic composites (7-8). The Avco Corporation 10MW electric air arc facility was used in this study (9). Linear recession rates and indepth temperatures were recorded to calculate the relative ablative and thermal efficiencies of the composites. The specimens were cross-sectioned to examine their physical appearance. Each material contained an outer porous char layer, an underlying thermally degraded region and an intact (unheated) region. The ablated rayon-based carbon fabric/phenolic specimen was more porous in the surface region and the carbon fabric plies were distorted from their original 20° orientation. The developmental carbon fabric/phenolics had a denser charred surface layer, and, their porosity was more uniform in distribution and pore size.

Normalized ablation rates for the commercial and developmental carbon fabric reinforced phenolics were as follows. The commercial carbon fabric/phenolics exhibited ablation rates up to 34% higher than baseline rayon-based carbon/phenolics. On the other hand, the developmental carbon fabric/phenolics had ablation rates up to 22% less than the baseline composite. Developmental PAN-based carbon/phenolics exhibited the lowest ablation rate.

The insulative features of the composites were also measured by thermocouples in the specimens and measuring in-depth temperatures during ablation. The pitch-based composites were more conductive than baseline composites, which was expected from previously measured composite thermal conductivities. In contrast to this feature, the developmental PAN-based carbon fabric/phenolic composite was five percent better than the baseline composite.

Density. The newly available carbon fabric/phenolics had only a slightly higher composite density compared to state-of-the-art rayon-based carbon/phenolics. This was due to the higher density fiber and greater areal weight of the PAN-based and pitch-based cloths.

Thermal Conductivity. Carbon fabrics derived from high temperature fired yarns and tows are quite crystalline and hence thermally conductive. Composites containing these reinforcements also conduct heat at a rapid rate, depending upon the fabric content and its orientation (10-11). Phenolic composites with commercial carbon fabrics were shown to have conductivities at 150°F (66°C) which ranged from 6.0 to 6.8 Btu-in/hr-ft²-°F (0.86-0.98 W/m-°K). As noted in Figure 3, the developmental carbon fabric reinforced phenolics had significantly lower

conductivity values. Through-the-thickness heat conductivity values for the pitch-based and PAN-based carbon fabric composites were only 4.6 Btu-in/hr-ft²-°F (0.66 W/m-°K) and 3.8 Btu-in/hr-ft²-°F (0.55 w/m^o-K), respectively. Insulative features of the developmental carbon fabric/phenolics were maintained at higher temperatures.

Thermal Expansion. The phenolic composites had a relatively low thermal expansion in the circumferential (hoop) and axial directions because of the restraining action of the reinforcement. Peak values less than 0.0013 in/in (mm/mm) were typically measured up to 1,400°F (760°C). In the radial direction however, peak expansion values from room temperature to 800°F (427°C) ranged upwards to 0.008 in/in (mm/mm) for the developmental PAN/phenolic composite and a high of 0.024 in/in (mm/mm) for commercially available rayon-based carbon/phenolics.

Specific Heat. The specific heat of the carbon/phenolics ranged from 0.24 to 0.27 Btu/lb-°F (1.00 J/kg-°K) at 150°F (66°C) and 0.33 to 0.38 Btu/lb-°F (1.38-1.59 J/kg-°K) at 450°F (232°C). These thermophysical property differences were attributed primarily to differences in fabric content of the composites.

Mechanical Properties. Hoop (circumferential) tensile properties were measured for six different tapewrapped carbon fabric/phenolic composites. The best composite strength and strain properties were exhibited by unfilled (U) rayon-based carbon/phenolics. Composites containing carbon powder (F) had somewhat lower strength and strain characteristics. Composites containing PAN-based and pitch-based carbon fabrics had similar strength properties, but wide differences in strain-to-failure levels.

Elevated temperatures had only a minor effect on the tensile and compressive properties of tapewrapped carbon/phenolic composites up to about 300°F (149°C). With increasing temperatures to 500°F (260°C), the strength and moduli values decreased and the strain-to-failure increased. Composites containing commercially available carbon fabrics exhibited a strength reductions up to 25% at 500°F (260°C). Even lower strength values were noted for the developmental fabric reinforced composites, i.e., on the order of 40%. Composite moduli values were not significantly affected up to 300°F (149°C), but slight increases were noted for some materials due to increased resin cross-linking. At 500°F (260°C), moduli reductions up to about 47% were noted with the greatest decreases evident in the developmental fabric reinforced composites. As expected, the strain-to-failure values increased continuously with temperatures up to 500°F (260°C). Compared to room temperature values, a 30 to 40% increase in strain at 500°F (260°C) was noted for the commercial fabric containing composites. These composite temperature effects were due primarily to the resin components. In the case of interlaminar shear strengths, reduced properties were likely due to resin, matrix-fiber and expansion coefficient effects. Figure 4 illustrates the influence of temperatures up to 500°F (260°C) on the interlaminar shear strengths of six different phenolic composites. PAN- and pitch-based carbon fabric composites had the lowest shear values at maximum test temperature, which were on the order of 1,500 psi (10.3 MPa) to 2,100 psi (14.5 MPa). Further investigations are necessary to isolate the individual effects of the constituents on shear properties (12).

Summary and Conclusions

Plastic composites containing commercially available carbon fabrics and phenolic resins exhibited suitable ablative and insulative properties for typical thermal protective applications. Significant improvements in insulative properties were demonstrated. Specialty carbon fabrics were manufactured from yarn, which was pyrolyzed at nonstandard temperatures. These developmental polyacrylonitrile and pitch-based carbon fabrics were shown to have high carbon contents, high densities, low thermal conductivities, high electrical resistivities, high tensile strengths, and handling characteristics suitable for laminates and tapewrapped composites.

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TYPICAL PROPERTIES OF COMMERCIAL AND DEVELOPMENTAL 8-HS CARBON FABRICS

FABRIC

PRECURSOR	VISCOSE RAYON	POLYACRYLONITRILE		MESOPHASE PITCH	
AVAILABILITY	COMMERCIAL	COMMERCIAL	DEVELOPMENTAL	COMMERCIAL	DEVELOPMENTAL
FILAMENT COUNT/ YARN BUNDLE	720	3000	3000	2000	1400
PLIES/YARN	1	1	1	1	1

PROPERTIES

WEIGHT	oz/sq_yd	8.3	11.0	10.8	16.2	10.1
	kg/mm ²	0.24	0.37	0.37	0.55	0.34
THICKNESS	in	0.018	0.027	0.028	0.028	0.018
	mm	0.457	0.686	0.711	0.711	0.457
THREAD COUNT	ends/in	52	24	24	21	26
		49	23	24	19	24
WARP	ends/5 cm	102	47	47	41	51
		97	45	47	37	47
BREAK STRENGTH	lbf/in	43	390	243	155	58
		30	355	227	135	40
WARP	N/m	4.9	44.1	27.5	17.5	6.6
		3.9	40.1	25.7	15.3	4.5

TABLE 1

FIGURE 1. AXIAL THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY OF CARBON FIBERS.

FIGURE 2. SCHEMATIC OF THE TAPEWRAPPING PROCESS.

FIGURE 3. RADIAL THERMAL CONDUCTIVITIES OF 20° TAPEWRAPPED COMPOSITES.

FIGURE 4. INTERLAMINAR SHEAR STRENGTHS OF 20° TAPEWRAPPED COMPOSITES.